

ENVIRONMENTAL
PHYSICS GROUP

NEWSLETTER

No. 7

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THE INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS

From the Editor	3
Committee News: Education	4
Committee Views: Neil Roberts	5
Research Focus	
SERC/AFRC Clean Technology Programme	6
News and Information	
TIGER Report; Energy Technology Newsletter; The NERC and Atmospheric Chemistry	8
UK Global Environmental Change	9
Book Review	10
Recent Publications	11
Future Events	
EPG Meetings	13
Other Meetings	14
The EPG Committee	16

Contributions

Contributions, news items or meeting notices are welcome from members and non-members alike and should be sent to:

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Parks Road, Oxford OX1 3PJ
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The deadline for issue number 8 is **31 January, 1994**.

EPG Membership

IoP/EPG membership enquiries are encouraged from both physicists and non-physicists with an interest in topics in "Environmental Physics". For further details contact:

The Membership Manager
(Mr David Foulkes)

The Institute of Physics
47 Belgrave Square,
London SW1X 8QX
Tel: (071) 235 6111 Fax: (071) 259 6002
e-mail: iop@uk.ac.ulcc

Welcome to newsletter number 7

Although I did not intend that the newsletter should have a particular theme for each issue, it seems that this time I have collected several pieces with a bias toward pollution control and air quality monitoring. In the first of a new, and I hope regular, feature called *Research Focus*, Eric Winiarski outlines the aims and objectives of **SERC/AFRC Clean Technology Programme**. Our book review concerns air pollution from motor vehicles (a rather contentious issue at least according to the *Independent on Sunday*, 10 October) and I have also included short summaries of two reports currently available. One deals with the official view of Cleaner Technology and the other with Atmospheric Chemistry research in the NERC. I hope you find them both interesting and useful.

Most of you will have received your October issue of *Physics World* by now and with it some information about the 1994 **Physics Congress** in Brighton. Members should note that **the EPG will be hosting a one day meeting at the Congress** although we are not mentioned in the brochure. It was confirmed only recently and therefore missed inclusion. However, I can tell you that we have been allocated **Tuesday, 12 April** so put it in your diary **now**. The programme has yet to be decided for this meeting but we intend it to have a theme based on what physics can do to help solve some of the environmental problems we have now and will face in the near future. Our primary goal is to emphasize the positive role a physicist will have in environmental issues.

As you may have noticed in the last issue there has been a slight change in the EPG Committee after the AGM. **Graham Alcock** resigned recently and has been replaced by **Mike Smithson**, also of the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory at Bidston. Mike studied physics at the University of Bradford and graduated in 1978. He completed a PhD in nuclear structure physics and remained at Bradford to do post-doctoral research and spent one year as a lecturer in the physics department. Between 1985 and 1987 he worked as a research scientist at the Clinton P Anderson Meson Physics Facility in New Mexico doing research in intermediate energy physics, before returning to the U.K. as a Senior Research Associate at the S.E.R.C Daresbury Laboratory. In 1990 he changed his field of study to oceanography and moved to the N.E.R.C. Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory on Merseyside. His current interests are in ocean circulation and tides, with emphasis in the south Atlantic and Southern Oceans.

More exciting developments !

You will be pleased to know that the University of London's Examination and Assessment Council (ULCEA) is commissioning us to develop an Environmental Physics option as part of its restructures A level Physics provision. The Sub-Committee will be meeting with the Chief Examiner (Mrs. Susan Oldcorn) on Saturday 25 September at the IoP to plan the way forward. Our work with the Oxford and Cambridge Schools Examinations Board continues to progress, and the time-scale for both exam boards is tight. Schemes of work and resource materials for teachers need to be in place in schools and colleges by September, 1994.

In spite of the increasing modularization of many curriculum areas, there are plans afoot for further radical developments in Post-16 Science provision. With the foundations that we are laying the Sub-Committee will be in a strong position to participate in new initiatives as they come 'on line'.

We are currently seeking sources of funding for developing curriculum materials that will enhance the effective teaching and learning on the part of teachers and students. If any of our readers could help us in locating possible sources we would like to hear from them.

The next meeting of the EPG Education Sub-Committee will be at **noon on Saturday, 20 November, 1993** at:

*Withington Girls' High School
Wellington Road, Fallowfield, Manchester*

EPG members and interested parties are very welcome.

Peter Hughes

Chair, EPG Education Sub-Committee

Any suggestions for possible sources for funding the work Peter has mentioned here should be sent to him at the following address:

*Kingsway College,
Sidmouth Street, London WC1H 8JB
Tel: 071 278 0541, Fax: 081 208 3421*

Hello from a new Committee member.

During my studies for a B.Sc. in Physics with Geophysics I grew fascinated by the suggestion that the extinction of various species was related to the fact that the Earth's magnetic field exhibits reversals of its polarity. For my Ph.D., and several years after, I studied records of polarity reversals as preserved in geological formations, undertaking sampling expeditions, and working in laboratories in Australia, U.S.A., South Africa, Lesotho, Iceland and France. Then in 1988 I opted for something of a change. I obtained an M.Sc. in Medical Physics and subsequent funding from Shell Research Ltd to set up facilities for the computer based analysis of medical images at the Magnetic Resonance Research Centre of the University of Liverpool. This is where I am today; I am enjoying and feeling a sense of purpose in placing modern design based stereological methods in the hands of clinicians in order to facilitate the unbiased and efficient quantification of human growth and the monitoring of the effects of treatment on disease.

What have I learnt from working as a physicist in these two seemingly different roles with the common thread of magnetic fields? The magnitude of the natural magnetic field of the Earth is of the order 50 micro-Tesla. During reversal, essentially it disappears, meaning that cosmic rays from outer space are no longer channeled down to the Earth's surface at the North and South Poles. Mutation rates may have increased at such times. Furthermore, changes in the direction of the field have led ocean dwelling micro-organisms up, instead of down, in search of food, and so brought about their extinction. Clinical Magnetic Resonance Imaging systems, use magnetic fields that are typically 30,000 times stronger than the natural magnetic field to produce high resolution images of sections through the human body, with remarkable contrast between the different soft tissues. As understood at present, and there is no reason to be unduly pessimistic, the modality induces no irreversible effects on human physiology and yet produces abundant benefits to Radiologists in enabling them to make clinical diagnoses.

I see the challenge that confronts the Physicist as the challenge to understand better the phenomenon with which he or she is working, and to appreciate the ways in which it can be used positively. To be aware of the environmental changes it may produce, and to retain a wonder for its working in a time, on a scale and with a purpose beyond our own careers.

Neil Roberts

*Magnetic Resonance Research Centre
University of Liverpool*

AFRC/SERC Clean Technology Programme

The Agricultural and Food Research Council (AFRC) and the Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC) in cooperation with the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) are working together to stimulate research towards new clean technologies and techniques. Clean technology is defined as products and processes that inherently forestall pollution by preventing the formation or release of dangerous or unpleasant by-products and by improving the efficiency of use of primary products. It aims at creating wealth while respecting the environment.

The programme encourages scientists and engineers to "think clean" by taking into consideration issues of sustainability, energy efficiency and waste minimisation in planning their research.

The AFRC/SERC Clean Technology Unit was set up in 1990 to coordinate and focus research aimed at such new technologies, or, at a lower priority, the fundamental redesign of existing processes so that they are inherently cleaner. Research on the clean-up of pollution from the past ("retrofits") and end-of-pipe technology to remove pollutants is clearly important, but will not usually require special encouragement. Indeed such research can and will feature in the programme of existing SERC and AFRC committees and boards as part of their own portfolio of environmentally-related research grants.

The councils have identified a series of specific research targets and themes to help the research community develop ideas for clean technology. The first three targets, launched in February 1992, are the **Clean synthesis of "effect" chemicals**, **The redesign of farming as an engineering process** and **Harnessing Photosynthesis**. Three further targets have now been identified:

- **Life cycle analysis (LCA)** - Techniques which attempt to identify systematically all the environmental loads associated with a product, or more generally, any human activity. LCA has been identified as a key topic underlying any discussion of how clean any technology is.
- **Cities and sustainability** - An integrated socio-technical approach to identify and then test the efficacy of policies and practices - along with technologies required to deliver them - for limiting unsustainability and promoting sustainability in cities. A research programme jointly with the ESRC was launched on 7 April, 1993.
- **Waste reduction at source** - Promoting waste minimisation; research leading to cleaner products and manufacturing processes which avoid, eliminate or reduce

waste usually within the confines of the production unit. The report on this target will be available in November, 1993.

In addition to these specific targets, research is also encouraged on three underlying themes which are relevant to clean technologies in general. These generic themes are:

- **fundamental work relevant to major advances in clean combustion** (but not, for example, incremental advances in technology for scrubbing flue gases);
- **electrochemistry**, for example, as applied to novel fuel cells;
- **novel methods of analysis and measurement**, particularly of trace quantities of pollutants.

Outside these specific targets and themes, the Unit remains keen to hear from academics who have really innovative ideas which could form the basis of a new clean technology. Ideas which cross the boundaries between the conventional scientific and engineering disciplines are particularly welcome.

High quality graduates and postgraduates will be an important source of the skilled manpower necessary for the introduction of clean technologies. The programmes education and training policy utilize existing Research Council schemes such as the allocation of Standard Research Studentships in addition to the award of Senior Research Fellowships specifically for clean technology, in collaboration with the Royal Society of Engineering.

Copies of reports on each of the research targets and further information about the **Clean Technology Programme** is available from :

AFRC/SERC Clean Technology Unit
SERC, Polaris House, North Star Avenue,
Swindon SN2 1ET
Tel: (0793) 411122 Fax: (0793) 411020

Eric Winiarski
Clean Technology Unit

Readers interested in the development and implementation of Clean Technology might also be interested in a recent report from the Advisory Council on Science and Technology (ACOST), called *Cleaner Technology*. Further details are given on page 11.

TIGER Annual Report

The Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research (TIGER) have recently published a Programme report for 1990–1992. It includes reports on the many aspects of a highly complex, multi-component scientific programme, and provides a summary of the overall aims and objectives of the TIGER initiative. Apart from that, it has one of the most striking cover pictures of a real tiger I have ever seen!

Complementary copies are restricted but, in my opinion, the price of £9 is a small sum to pay given the amount of information provided and the quality of the production.

Copies are available from:

*TIGER Programme Office,
Institute of Hydrology, Maclean Building,
Crowmarsh Gifford, Wallingford Oxon OX10 8BB*

International Energy Agency: Energy Technology Newsletter

For anyone involved with, or interested in, current developments in the energy generation, conversion, use and misuse on a world-wide scale, the **IEA: Energy Technology Newsletter** is a 'must' for your reading list. It is typically around 50 pages long and contains detailed information about the activities and publications of the IEA and provides a comprehensive review of world-wide conferences and meetings organised by the various IEA working parties. Subject areas covered include: Energy research and technology, energy end-use technologies, fossil fuels, renewable energy technologies, and fusion Power.

For further information contact:

*Mr T. Kudama International Energy Agency (IEA),
2 rue André-Pascal, 75775 Paris Cedex 16, France
Fax: ++33-1-4524-9988*

NERC: Chemistry in the Atmosphere

Chemistry in the Atmosphere is the final report of the NERC Special Topics Programme in Atmospheric Chemistry and describes its achievements and outlines the future aims in NERC's Atmospheric Chemistry Research. The programme was initiated some 10 years ago with the primary goal of using the expertise available in our universities and research institutes to develop new techniques and to study many different aspects of

atmospheric chemistry in both the laboratory and in the field. In this the programme has been successful and has provided a solid foundation for future atmospheric research supported by the NERC.

In content, the report outlines the theme, history and methodology of atmospheric chemistry in general and of the Special Topics Programme in particular. It describes some of the facilities available for this work, the additional activities inspired by the Programme and some of the plans for future research projects.

For further information contact:

*Programme Director for Atmospheric Sciences,
Marine and Atmospheric Sciences Directorate, NERC
Polaris House, North Star Avenue,
Swindon SN2 1EU
Tel: (0793) 411753, Fax: (0793) 411 545*

UK Global Environmental Research (UK GER)

The October issue of the UK GER newsletter, *The Globe*, is now available. This issue focuses on *Population and Environmental Health* and contains two major articles dealing first with global population trends and, secondly, world reproductive health. Combined they give a fascinating insight into the complexity of this interaction and how this relates to environmental issues. The next issue of *The Globe* will be published in November and will have the theme *Polar Sciences* whilst issue 17 (January, 1994) will deal with *Global Environmental Change and its contribution to Science Education*.

The GER have also recently produced a report on behalf of the UK International Agency Committee on Environmental Change (IACGEC) entitled **Global Environmental Change: The UK Research Framework 1993**. It updates an earlier report published in April 1993, and 'widens the debate on global environmental issues through preliminary measures of "impacts and response measures" '.

Copies of both **The Globe** and the IACGEC report can be obtained from:

*UK GER Office
Polaris House, North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU*

Air Pollution From Road Vehicles

Transport and Road Research Laboratory: State of Art Review/1

L H Watkins HMSO 1991 £ 17.50

This book of about 150 pages provides a useful introduction to: the sources of engine exhaust emissions and their measurement, worldwide emissions legislation, the environmental effect of legislated and non-legislated emissions, engine emission control technology, and methods of surveying and modelling atmospheric pollution from vehicles.

Chapter 2 reviews the techniques for emissions measurements, both in the laboratory and in the field although the data presented on engine emissions should be treated as indicative, since so much depends on the engine operating point and engine management system calibration.

Emissions Legislation (Chapter 3) is of course an area subject to regular change. The USA legislation is covered to 1988 for Light Duty Vehicles, and until 1994 for Heavy Duty Commercial Vehicles. There is no mention of the stricter Californian legislation, which is often a useful indication of subsequent US Legislation. In Europe, the legislation ends with proposals for 1990. None the less there are useful discussions on the relevance of the legislation, and the requirements (eg durability). There is also a review of air quality, and this leads to a discussion of fuel quality, notably benzene and lead restrictions in gasoline, and the sulphur levels and cetane number of diesel fuel.

Chapter 4 on Environmental Effects encompasses: the toxic properties of various pollutants, concentrations measured at a wide range of locations, issues such as acid rain, and a short resume of the greenhouse effect. The next chapter on Emission Control Technology aims to cover a very wide field in about 40 pages. In the case of spark ignition engines there is no mention of emissions during engine warm-up, and only a brief mention of catalyst performance prior to light-off. This is unfortunate, as the emissions immediately after starting are becoming of increasing importance. The final chapter includes surveys of air quality, people's subjective response to pollutants, and models for predicting pollutant concentration in the environment.

Overall, this is a useful and cheap book, that provides a good introduction and overview of the issues concerning air pollution from road vehicles. There is a wealth of tabulated data, and (unusually) estimates of the costs associated with implementing changes to both vehicles and their fuels.

Dr Richard Stone
Fellow of Somerville College

Department of Engineering Science
University of Oxford

Environmental Sensors

IoP Publishing,
Bristol

The publishing arm of the Institute of Physics is about to launch a new monthly newsletter called *Environmental Sensors*. It will provide the latest news on emerging sensor technology including biosensors, fibre optics and silicon ISFETs, company and product announcements, government and international initiatives, market developments and predictions plus book reviews and forthcoming events.

Environmental Sensors also contains regular articles by leading experts from the UK, Germany and the USA. These editors, Robert Bogue, Guido Tschulena and Jo Ann McDonald, deliver authoritative international commentary. Robert Bogue is a physicist who spent the first 14 years of his career in industry before undertaking numerous consultancy projects for UK government organisations, research establishments and sensor manufacturers. He has over 40 publications to his name. Guido Tschulena is an independent consultant who holds the lectureship on sensor technology at the Fachhochschule, Friedberg in Germany. He was formerly senior research scientist at Battelle Europe in Frankfurt. Jo Anne McDonald is a leading commentator on America's advance technologies, including biosensors, optoelectronics, cryoelectronics, ASIC design and micro/millimetre wave systems.

Environmental Sensors is essential reading for all instrument manufacturers, equipment users, technical directors, government regulators, environmental impact auditors and consultants whose activities have an impact on the environment. A special discount of 30% is available off the full price of £ 195 for subscriptions received before December.

For more details or a free sample copy contact:

Geraldine Pounsford
IOP Publishing, Techno House, Redcliffe Way,
Bristol, BS1 6NX, UK.
Tel: (0272) 297481, Fax: (0272) 294318.

Tina Monk
IoP Publishing

World Energy Outlook

OECD, Paris

Available in the UK through HMSO stockists priced at £ 22

This is a new study in which the International Energy Agency examines the evolution of world energy markets through 2010.

"World demand for energy is expected to increase significantly through the first decade of the next century as population and real incomes rise. Demand will increase in OECD countries but growth will be strongest in non-OECD countries - particularly China, India and the dynamic Asian economies. By 2010, OECD countries will account for less than half of total oil consumption. On the supply side, the study projects a large increase in the role of natural gas, especially in Europe. The impacts of these and other supply and demand developments on energy use patterns will be significant. As the world enters the 21st century, electricity will become an increasingly important energy form. How electricity is generated, as well as how transportation systems develop, will affect how successful countries will be in meeting their energy needs and achieving their environmental objectives."

OECD Publications

Cleaner Technology

Advisory Council on Science and Technology (ACOST)

HMSO 1992 72 pages (including annexes) £ 11.95

Although not a *Recent Publication* in the strictest sense, this report is still a highly informative text giving the official view of *Clean Technology (CT)* and its role in the future of industrial UK. It describes what Government should do to encourage industry to develop the most efficient environmental solutions. It is suggested that this might be achieved through a series of measures which include the setting of clear and long-term environmental targets; providing a suitable and efficient framework for regulation and enforcement; supporting strong environmental science based activity and linking this with industry; and providing a framework of support for industrial development and take-up of environmental technology.

Throughout this report the reader is reminded that although the major benefit is a cleaner environment one should not forget that there is a major and rapidly growing world market for CT know-how and that this should be exploited by UK industry. However, it also gives a broader view to the whole question of how world industrial activity can develop successfully without seriously interfering with the environment. *GH*

EPG Meetings:**Pollution Transport through Unsaturated Soils****12 January, 1994***Venue: The Institute of Physics, 47 Belgrave Square, London*

This afternoon meeting of the Environmental Physics Group is being organised in collaboration with the British Soil-water Physics Group to consider the physical processes involved in the transport of pollutants through unsaturated soils. There will be five invited speakers who will deal specifically with problems associated with nitrate transport, pesticide movement, migration of radioactive materials and oil spillages, following an introductory talk outlining the physics of transport processes in unsaturated soils.

The number of participants will be limited to 65 because of the size of the lecture room, and pre-registration will be necessary. Further details from:

Prof. E G Youngs*Silsoe College, Cranfield University, Silsoe, Bedford MK45 4DT**Tel: (0525) 860428 Fax: (0525) 861417***Environmental Issues in Physics Education****29 - 31 March, 1994***Venue: University of Reading*

This is the 1994 Annual Conference of the Education Group of the Institute of Physics and has been organised in conjunction with the Environmental Physics Group and in association with the Royal Meteorological Society's Education Committee. It is intended that the conference will provide a forum for the discussion of the opportunities to exploit the use of physics in addressing current environmental issues and it will examine how these issues are being used to teach Physics and the key role physicists have in trying to understand them. The very nature of the conference theme involves a wide range of topics including global environmental issues (i.e. global warming, ozone hole and circulation modelling); sensors, measurement and processing; renewable energy resources; pollution modelling; environmental physics in teaching; the responsibility of physicists to the environment.

Contributions addressing the above, or related, topics are invited from members of schools, HE/FE institutions and examination boards and may be either for oral or poster presentation. Offers of contributions should be sent to:

Mr John Kerr*Katharine Lady Berkely's School,**Wotton under Edge, Gloucestershire GL12 8RB**Tel: (0453) 842227 ext. 236 Fax: (0453) 845480*

Contributions should arrive not later than **2 November, 1993**. Full details of the conference and registration will be circulated to Education Group members in January 1994. Non-members should contact the *Meetings and Conferences Department* at IoP Headquarters in London.

The Global Energy and Water Cycle **18–22 July, 1994**

Call for Abstracts: Deadline 31 October, 1993

Venue: The Royal Society, London

This conference will bring together meteorologists, hydrologists and others across Europe involved in the study, via observations, modelling and theory, of processes affecting the energy and water cycle on scales ranging from that of the global circulation to small scale processes whose effects are felt both regionally and globally.

This meeting is organised by the UK GEWEX Forum and is supported by The Royal Society, The Royal Meteorological Society, The British Hydrological Society, The Remote Sensing Society and others including the Environmental Physics Group. It will consist of both invited and contributed papers and posters covering areas related to the water and energy cycle. Session headings include atmospheric processes, precipitation measurement and analysis, land-atmosphere interactions, ocean-atmosphere interactions, continental-scale water budgets, and global modelling.

For further information contact:

*The Executive Secretary, The Royal Meteorological Society,
104 Oxford Road, Reading, Berks RG1 7LJ*

Other Meetings:

Sea Level Changes: Measurements and Analysis **9–10 December, 1993**

Contact: PSMSL, Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory, Bidston Observatory

Birkenhead, Merseyside L43 7RA

Fax: (051) 653 6269

**Instrumentation and Data Analysis
in Environmental Science**

11–22 April, 1994

Contact: Dr Stephen Hicks, Dept. of Biological Sciences,

University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL

Tel: (0203) 523540 Fax: (0203) 523701

Buildings and the Environment

16–20 May, 1994

Venue: Building Research Establishment, Garston, Watford

Organised by CIB Task Group 8 (Environmental Assessment of Buildings).

Buildings are responsible for a large part of man's impact on the environment, indoors, locally and globally. The purpose of this conference is to bring together the latest research on understanding and assessing this impact, and to identify areas where future research is needed. Topics to be covered include the global impacts of buildings on the environment such as the total emissions of CO_2 and other pollutants due to energy use and the technology to avoid the use or release of CFCs; the use of resources in materials and components, lifecycle analysis, recycling and reuse of building materials and economy of water use; the neighbourhood and the ecological impact of building site choice, reuse of land, effective town planning to reduce the impact or use of vehicles, the effect of buildings on the local climate, visual impact and overshadowing and sunlight reflection; the internal environment and criteria for human health such as indoors pollutants, noise, odors, humidity, temperature and lighting; case studies of environmentally friendly buildings will be considered including design studies and built examples; the methods for assessing the environmental impact of a building and energy labelling.

The deadline for contributions to this conference has passed but for information on attending contact:

Andrew Cripps,

c/o Building Research Establishment,

Garston, Watford, WD2 7JR

Global Forum '94

25 June–3 July, 1994

Global Forum '94 has the theme "Cities and Sustainable Development – Strategies for a Sustainable Future". The programme includes an academic conference examining the implementation of Agenda 21, adopted at the UNCED in Rio, June 1993. It will consist of a number of parallel workshops and specialist speaker sessions.

Further details are available from:

Global Forum Conference Organiser,

Dept. of Env. and Geog. Studies, Manchester Metropolitan University,

John Dalton Extension Building, Chester Street, Manchester M1 5GD

Tel: (061) 247 1583, Fax: (061) 236 7383

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Institute of Hydrology,
Wallingford, Oxon OX10 8BB
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University of Greenwich

Dr Anne Wheldon Energy Group, Department of Engineering,
University of Reading

Professor Edward Youngs Silsoe College,
Cranfield Institute of Technology

† Newsletter Editor: See contents page for full address.

‡ Graham Alcock has resigned from the Committee and the Committee has co-opted Dr Mike Smithson, Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory in his place.